

Reality - which reality?

Reality, truth, being, ... We use these words daily at million different occasions and contexts. Yet, their meaning is far from clearly defined and understood, even if they attempt to define us and the whole Universe.

There are several definitions of 'reality', but one stands out for its clarity perspective: the 'ontological objective reality'. It is what is left when we remove all possible observers (reality) and its content is independent from anybody who could potentially peek at it (objectivity). The barebone existence...

However, this lofty definition leaves us high and dry if we want to try saying anything about what this 'ontological objective reality' actually could be. The castle's high walls force us to make some assumptions if we are to make any progress. Assumption number one - there is a physical objective reality out there, not just 'Matrix'-style void. Assumption two - the scientifically obtained and agreed body of current knowledge represents fairly well the facts about it. If we don't accept these two assumptions, this essay stops here...

Let's take a timeline view of this objective reality. It can be expected to have:

- a) the 'now' - this is the current macrostate point in the Universe's time,
- b) the 'past' - as I have attempted to show in the essay "Can Time Be Reversed? Information, irreversibility, and a misplaced paradox" ([10.5281/zenodo.18402210](https://zenodo.org/record/18402210)), our Universe suffers from permanent memory loss regarding the microphysical path which has led to the 'now', simply because all the details of that path were never recorded. The objective reality has 'nows' but immediately forgets about their 'pasts',
- c) the 'future' - any interaction of entangled particles causes non-local quantum decoherence, irreversibly changing the trajectory of the Universe in, practically, an unpredictable way. It is an inherently unstable place. So, future exists as a spectrum of all possible paths, not as single determined trajectory. It is potentiality, not reality...

If we sum it all up, we arrive at the conclusion that any physical, ontologically objective reality consists only of 'nows'...

I can already hear indignant shouts: "but what about my beer, my stolen car, my check to be cashed..." - aren't they real enough? Sure, they are. But because observers (not necessarily human) actively record their past and shape their future - inevitably embedding in them their own biases - these are the only pasts and futures that exist beyond the ontological 'now'. Small wonder that some wise man arrived at the famous definition of truth* as the "justified true belief"...

Why? Because without the active, uniquely biased observers the physical, ontologically objective reality has only the singular 'now'...

*The definition of truth as "justified true belief" comes from Plato's dialogue "Theaetetus" (c. 369 BCE), where Socrates explores the conditions for knowledge. It resurfaced thanks to Edmund Gettier's paper (1963): "Is Justified True Belief Knowledge?". He actually approached it by formulating counterexamples.

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